

Assessment of the Use of Prophylactic Antibiotics in Women Undergoing Elective Caesarean Section: A Comparative StudySimpi Shilpa¹, Sweta Kumari², Seema Singh³¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India³Assistant Professor and HOD, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The objectives of the study were to audit and implement the use of prophylactic antibiotics in women undergoing elective caesarean section.**Methods:** This comparative, prospective, hospital based study was conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology for the period of 24 months. Patients were randomly divided on alternate number basis in 2 groups (Group A and Group B) each consisted of 100 patients.**Results:** Mean age was 25.5±4.6 years in group A & 24.6±3.4 years in group B. BMI at the time of admission was 26.4±6.3 kg/m² & 27.3± 5.4 kg/m² in group A & B respectively. Mean duration of surgery was 41.9±6.4 min in group A & 47.3±5.5 in group B. Average blood loss in both groups was comparable. Mean days of hospitalisation was 4.8±3.7 days & 5.7±2.9 days in group A & B respectively. Most common indication for elective LSCS was previous LSCS followed (42% and 38%) by primi with CPD (24% v/s 22%). In the group A prophylactic antibiotic prophylaxis was given to 20 women (40%) and was not given to 30 women (60%). In group B, out of 50 women of this 45 (90%) of women received prophylactic antibiotic before elective LSCS. Out of 20 women who received antibiotic in group A, 40% received antibiotic within 1 hour and 12 cases (60%) received more than 1 hour before procedure. Out of 45 women in group A, 38 (84.45%) women received antibiotic within 1 hour, 8 received more than 1 hour (15.55%). In the group A, majority of the women received amoxicillin clavulanic acid 1.2 gm IV /Inj cefotaxime based on the policy formulated based on the antibiogram of the hospital.**Conclusion:** This study showed single dose antibiotic prophylaxis is as effective as conventional multi dose antibiotic therapy. It is cost effective, antibiotic resistance of microorganisms can be prevented, reduces patient side effects, nursing staff work.**Keywords:** prophylactic antibiotic, caesarian delivery, ceftriaxone, ampicillin and metronidazoleThis is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Caesarean section is one of the commonly performed obstetric procedure. Following caesarean delivery (CD), maternal morbidity and mortality may result from a number of infections including endometritis, urinary tract infection (UTI) and surgical site infection (SSI). [1] The use of prophylactic antibiotics in women undergoing caesarean section reduced the incidence of wound infection, endometritis and serious infectious complications by 60% to 70%. [2] ACOG has recommended that antibiotic be given within 1 hour before the caesarean section for maternal benefit. [3] In spite of the guidelines several studies have shown that the hospital practices varies from no

preoperative antibiotic to various different classes of antibiotics. The timing of the antibiotic also varied depending on physician preference with no uniform protocols across hospital. [4,5]

In spite of the guidelines several studies have shown that the hospital practices varies from no preoperative antibiotic to various different classes of antibiotics. The timing of the antibiotic also varied depending on physician preference with no uniform protocols across hospital. [6,7] Clinical audit usually starts with a review of current clinical practice, progresses to setting standards for care as per a set guideline, monitoring practice against these standards, analyzing the findings and

implementation of new practices. [8] Although audits are a useful tool to change clinical practice very few audits have been carried regarding antibiotic prophylaxis for caesarean section. [9]

A Cochrane review from 2014 compared antibiotic prophylaxis with no prophylaxis and concluded that antibiotic prophylaxis decreased the risk for postpartal wound infection, endometritis and severe infectious complications by 60–70%. Prophylactic antibiotics are expected to work in conjunction with the antiseptic measures taken before and during surgery. Around 40%–60% of SSIs can be prevented with the use of proper antibiotic prophylaxis. The most commonly used types of antibiotics are penicillins, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, tetracyclines and macrolides, with each class including many drugs. [10] Around 40%–60% of SSIs can be prevented with the use of proper antibiotic prophylaxis. The most commonly used types of antibiotics are penicillins, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, tetracyclines and macrolides, with each class including many drugs. [10] Furthermore, two recently published randomised trials [11,12] consisting of 320 and 120 women respectively, also found no evidence of decreased postoperative morbidity and questioned the use of prophylactic antibiotics for women undergoing elective caesarean section.

The objectives of the study were to audit and implement the use of prophylactic antibiotics in women undergoing elective caesarean section.

Materials and Methods

This comparative, prospective, hospital based study was conducted in the department of obstetrics and Gynecology Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Science, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India for the period of 24 months.

Inclusion Criteria –

- Patients posted for elective LSCS, BMI <30, willing to participate in study & follow up for 3 months.
- The caesarean was considered elective when the procedure was performed in the absence of labor and before rupture of membrane.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women who had known or suspected hypersensitivity to cephalosporins

- Any co-existing diseases like diabetes mellitus, hypertension or cardiac problem that will require multi dose antibiotics
- Surgical procedure exceeding more than 90 minutes and if blood loss was more than 1500ml.

Patients received information about objective of present study prior to surgery and a written informed consent was obtained. Baseline assessment including vital signs, general physical, systemic and obstetric examination were performed. Routine blood (CBC, RBS, RFT) and urine analysis & if required urine culture and sensitivity, high vaginal swab culture and sensitivity were carried out. Patients were randomly divided on alternate number basis in 2 groups (Group A and Group B) each consisted of 100 patients.

Group A - patients received injection Ceftriaxone 1gm. intravenous stat at the time of induction of anesthesia.

Group B - patients received intravenous ampicillin and metronidazole for 1 day followed by oral for next 4 days.

Temperature monitoring, vital signs, abdominal, perineal examinations were performed daily till 7days. If body temperature was more than 101.0 F on 2 occasions 4 hours or more apart, excluding the night of surgery, it was considered as febrile morbidity and appropriate investigations were performed including urine culture, blood culture, high vaginal swab culture before starting appropriate multi dose antibiotics. Wound was inspected for superficial or deep infection, any pus discharge, surgical site abscess formation, wound dehiscence, vault haematoma and pelvic abscess. At discharge, patients were instructed to contact if they have any signs and symptoms of infection. All patients were followed up to 3 months at monthly intervals. Incidence of postoperative morbidity (febrile morbidity and infectious morbidity such as wound infection, chest infection, UTI, pelvic abscess and dehiscence of scar) was primary outcome.

Data was collected in pre-designed proforma & entered in SPSS for descriptive and analytical study. A p value of <0.05 was considered significant.

Results

Table 1: Characteristics of patients in two groups

	Group A	Group B
Mean age in years	25.5±4.6	24.6±3.4
BMI in kg/m ²	26.4±6.3	27.3± 5.4
Mean duration of surgery (min)	41.9±6.4	47.3±5.5
Mean blood loss (ml.)	632±58	655±65
Mean days of catheterization	1	1

Mean days of hospitalisation (days)	4.8±3.7	5.7±2.9
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Mean age was 25.5±4.6 years in group A & 24.6±3.4 years in group B. BMI at the time of admission was 26.4±6.3 kg/m² & 27.3± 5.4 kg/m² in group A & B respectively. Mean duration of surgery was 41.9±6.4 min in group A & 47.3±5.5 in group B. Average blood loss in both groups was comparable. Mean days of hospitalisation was 4.8±3.7 days & 5.7±2.9 days in group A & B respectively.

Table 2: Indication for CS

Parameters	Group A	Group B
Previous LSCS	21 (42%)	19 (38%)
CPD	12 (24%)	11 (22%)
BREECH	6 (12%)	5 (10%)
Fetal distress	7 (14%)	6 (12%)
PROM	6 (12%)	7 (14%)
Others	2 (4%)	3 (6%)

Most common indication for elective LSCS was previous LSCS followed (42% and 38%) by primi with CPD (24% v/s 22%).

Table 3: Antibiotic prophylaxis and Antibiotic prophylaxis type and duration

Categories	Group A	Group B	P Value
Received antibiotics	20 (40%)	45 (90%)	<0.00001
Did not receive antibiotics	30 (60%)	5 (10%)	
Antibiotic prophylaxis type and duration			
Within 1 hour	8 (40%)	38 (84.45)	<0.00001
More than 1 hour	12 (60%)	7 (15.55)	
Inj amoxicillin-clavulanic acid/ inj cefotaxime	11 (55%)	44 (88.88)	
Others	9 (45%)	10 (11.12%)	

In the group A prophylactic antibiotic prophylaxis was given to 20 women (40%) and was not given to 30 women (60%). In group B, out of 50 women of this 45 (90%) of women received prophylactic antibiotic before elective LSCS. Out of 20 women who received antibiotic in group A, 40% received antibiotic within 1 hour and 12 cases (60%) received more than 1 hour before procedure. Out of 45 women in group A, 38 (84.45%) women received antibiotic within 1 hour, 8 received more than 1 hour (15.55%). In the group A, majority of the women received amoxicillin clavulanic acid 1.2 gm IV /Inj cefotaxime based on the policy formulated based on the antibiogram of the hospital.

Discussion

Infectious morbidity is the most common complication following caesarean section with reported rates ranging from 18% to 83% [13], while that for vaginal delivery is less than 10%. [14] The potential of antibiotic prophylaxis has been studied extensively since the first controlled trial, reported by Miller and Crichton. [15] Over the last few decades a consistent increase has been observed in the rate of caesarean deliveries are noted worldwide & India. It is often argued that obstetricians also increasingly prefer for surgical birth than a normal birth due to multiple reasons as women not opting

for vaginal delivery, medicolegal issues, precious pregnancies, etc.

Mean age was 25.5±4.6 years in group A & 24.6±3.4 years in group B. BMI at the time of admission was 26.4±6.3 kg/m² & 27.3± 5.4 kg/m² in group A & B respectively. Mean duration of surgery was 41.9±6.4 min in group A & 47.3±5.5 in group B. Average blood loss in both groups was comparable. Mean days of hospitalisation was 4.8±3.7 days & 5.7±2.9 days in group A & B respectively. Most common indication for elective LSCS was previous LSCS followed (42% and 38%) by primi with CPD (24% v/s 22%). Across the globe, SSIs are associated with increased morbidity and mortality; sequelae include revision surgeries, poor quality of life, prolonged antibiotic treatment and rehabilitation, and associated lost work and productivity. Moreover, SSIs are associated with a substantial economic burden to the healthcare system as a result of increased length of hospital stay and increased risk of readmission. [16] Current strategies aimed at preventing SSIs include improved hygiene, aseptic surgical techniques, carrier screening, decolonization, application of antibiotics to the surgical site prior to wound closure, and intravenous antibiotic prophylaxis. [17]

In the group A prophylactic antibiotic prophylaxis was given to 20 women (40%) and was not given to

30 women (60%). In group B, out of 50 women of this 45 (90%) of women received prophylactic antibiotic before elective LSCS. Out of 20 women who received antibiotic in group A, 40% received antibiotic within 1 hour and 12 cases (60%) received more than 1 hour before procedure. Out of 45 women in group A, 38 (84.45%) women received antibiotic within 1 hour, 8 received more than 1 hour (15.55%). In the group A, majority of the women received amoxicillin clavulanic acid 1.2 gm IV /Inj cefotaxime based on the policy formulated based on the antibiogram of the hospital. Single dose antibiotic prophylaxis is well-established for abdominal and vaginal hysterectomy and cumulative meta-analysis data indicate the same. Perioperative antimicrobial prophylaxis has been advocated in surgical procedures, but recent guidelines and publications showed that single dose antibiotic prophylaxis is equally effective in clean, and clean contaminated surgical procedures. Following elective surgery, wound infection in patients who receive perioperative antibiotics (within 3 hours following skin incision) occurs in 1.4% compared to 0.6% in those who receive antibiotics within 2 hours before skin incision. [18]

The randomized, non-blinding clinical trial of 500 eligible participants compared IV single dose of gentamicin (3 mg/kg) plus metronidazole (500 mg) 30-60 minutes prior to CS with same regimen prior to the operation but continued for 24 hours. Pre-operative single dose antibiotic prophylaxis for emergency caesarean showed a lower cumulative incidence of surgical-site infection, a reduced staff workload and a minimized medication cost compared to multiple doses till 24 hours. [19] While one meta-analysis, which was based solely on elective cesarean delivery, did not find a risk reduction for any maternal outcome in favor of preoperative in comparison with postoperative antibiotic prophylaxis. [20]

Conclusion

This study showed single dose antibiotic prophylaxis is as effective as conventional multi dose antibiotic therapy. It is cost effective, antibiotic resistance of microorganisms can be prevented, reduces patient side effects, nursing staff work. Further knowledge of antibiotic susceptibility and resistant strains is to be considered while choosing antibiotic.

References

1. Berg CJ, Chang J, Callaghan WM, Whitehead SJ. Pregnancy-related mortality in the United States, 1991–1997. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 2003 Feb 1;101(2):289-96.
2. Smaill FM, Grivell RM. Antibiotic prophylaxis versus no prophylaxis for preventing infection

after cesarean section. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*. 2014(10).

3. ACOG Guidance: Antibiotic Prophylaxis during Labor and Delivery [Internet].
4. Pedersen TK, Blaakær J. Antibiotic prophylaxis in cesarean section. *Acta obstetrica et gynecologica scandinavica*. 1996 Jan 1; 75(6):537-9.
5. Dhar H, Al-Busaidi I, Rathi B, Nimre EA, Sachdeva V, Hamdi I. A study of post-caesarean section wound infections in a regional referral hospital, Oman. *Sultan Qaboos University Medical Journal*. 2014 May ;002014(2):e211.
6. Pedersen TK, Blaakaer J. Antibiotic prophylaxis in cesarean section. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. 1996 Jul; 75(6): 537-9.
7. Dhar H, Al-Busaidi I, Rathi B, Nimre EA, Sachdeva V, Hamdi I. A Study of Post-Caesarean Section Wound Infections in a Regional Referral Hospital, Oman. *Sultan Qaboos Univ Med J*. 2014 May;14(2): e211–7.
8. Costa ML, Cecatti JG, Milanez HM, Souza JP, Gülmezoglu M. Audit and feedback: Effects on professional obstetrical practice and healthcare outcomes in a university hospital. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. 2009; 88(7): 793-800.
9. Taylor GM. An audit of the implementation of guidelines to reduce wound infection following caesarean section. *Health Bull (Edinb)*. 2000 Jan; 58(1):38-44.
10. Green, Salah Gammouh Amman. Current International Evidence and Recommendations for Antibiotic Prophylaxis in Gynecological Procedures Review of the Cesarean Section Antibiotic Prophylaxis Program in Jordan and Workshop on Rational Medicine Use and Infection Control, 2012, 28.
11. Yip SK, Lau TK, Rogers MS. A study on prophylactic antibiotics in cesarean sections-is it worthwhile?. *Acta obstetrica et gynecologica Scandinavica*. 1997 Jan 1;76(6): 547-9.
12. Rizk DE, Nsanze H, Mabrouk MH, Mustafa N, Thomas L, Kumar M. Systemic antibiotic prophylaxis in elective cesarean delivery. *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics*. 1998 Jun 1;61(3):245-51.
13. Henderson E, Love EJ. Incidence of hospital-acquired infections associated with caesarean section. *Journal of hospital infection*. 1995 Apr 1;29(4):245-55.
14. GIBBS RS. Clinical risk factors for puerperal infection. *Obstetrics & Gynecology*. 1980 Mar 1;55(3):178S-83S.
15. Miller RD, Crichton D. Ampicillin prophylaxis in cesarean section. *S Afr J Obstet Gynecol*. 1968;6:69.
16. Patel H, Khoury H, Girgenti D, Welner S, Yu H. Burden of surgical site infections associated with select spine operations and involvement of

- Staphylococcus aureus. Surg Infect. 2017; 18(4):461-73.
17. Weiser MC, Moucha CS. The current state of screening and decolonization for the prevention of Staphylococcus aureus surgical site infection after total hip and knee arthroplasty. JBJS. 2015;97(17):1449-58.
 18. Lamont RF, Sobel JD, Kusanovic JP, Vaisbuch E, Mazaki-Tovi S, Kim SK, Uldbjerg N, Romero R. Current debate on the use of antibiotic prophylaxis for caesarean section. BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology. 2011 Jan;118(2):193-201.
 19. Lyimo FM, Massinde AN, Kidenya BR, Konje ET, Mshana SE. Single dose of gentamicin in combination with metronidazole versus multiple doses for prevention of post-caesarean infection at Bugando Medical Centre in Mwanza, Tanzania: a randomized, equivalence ,controlled trial. BMC pregnancy and childbirth. 2013 Dec;13(1):1-7.
 20. Zhang C, Zhang L, Liu X, Zhang L, Zeng Z, Li L, Liu G, Jiang H. Timing of antibiotic prophylaxis in elective caesarean delivery: a multi-center randomized controlled trial and meta-analysis. PLoS One. 2015 Jul 6;10(7):e 0129434.